

Percentage of spikelet sterility induced by high temperature under natural climatic condition in southeastern Sichuan, China.

Method	Daily mean temperature (°C)	Daily maximum temperature (°C)	Sterility (%)	Spikelets or panicles observed (no.)
Spikelet treatment	27.9 ± 1.02	32.4 ± 1.75	7.24 ± 1.64	11,984
	31.27 ± 1.12	36.35 ± 1.11	10.85 ± 2.05	7,719
Panicle treatment	27.2 ± 1.10	31.35 ± 2.39	14.87 ± 2.84	200
	30.87 ± 0.06	35.27 ± 0.25	21.93 ± 1.36	150

indicate that daily mean temperatures 30 °C or lower and daily maximum temperatures 35 °C or lower significantly affected spikelet sterility.

To determine the stages most sensitive to high temperature, we treated 2,636

spikelets at meiosis, 778 at pollen grain development stage, and 1,320 at flowering, using 35 °C for 4 h in the phytotron. This induced 4.1% sterility at meiosis, 5.3% at pollen grain development, and 15.8% at flowering.

The index of heat tolerance (% fertility at high temperature/ % sterility at normal temperature) for hybrid rices Shan You 2 and Ai You 2 were determined at 33, 35, and 37 °C in the phytotron. Heat tolerance for Shan You 2 was 1.05, 0.78, and 0.14; that for Ai You 2 was 0.84, 0.42, and 0.09, respectively. Thus Shan You 2 tolerated high temperature better than did Ai You 2.

Adopting high temperature-tolerant varieties and adjusting flowering times are strategies to avoid high temperature sterility. □

Adverse soils tolerance

Modified screening method for salt tolerance

Guo Wang-mo and Chen Rong-ye, Soil Science and Plant Nutrition Department, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI), Hangzhou, Zhejiang, China

We developed a practical method to screen rice varieties for salt tolerance, based on IRRI's screening techniques. Some modifications have been made:

1. Rice seedlings are planted in soil fertilized with NPK instead of raised in solution culture, simplifying the screening of more varieties at lower cost.
2. Screening is fixed at the 3-leaf stage to eliminate the unfavorable effects caused by 2-wk-old seedlings grown in different seasons.

3. At 4 wk after transplanting (WT) the plants are scored by both the percentage of dead leaves and the salt injury symptoms (visual), and IRRI's standard of score 2 and score 1 are merged into score 1.

We have tested 1,580 rice varieties, including some of IRRI's resistant and susceptible checks such as Nona Bokra, Pokkali, Kalarata, and Damodar, by this modified method. Results are similar to those with IRRI's technique. The procedure is as follows:

- Germinate rice seeds in demineralized water.
- Plant the pregerminated seeds in soil fertilized with NPK.
- Irrigate up to 1 cm depth until seedlings reach the 3-leaf stage.
- Pull the seedlings without injuring the roots, wash the roots in water, and select

four good uniform seedlings from each variety.

- Plant them in a tray (41 × 27 × 13 cm) filled with 7 kg clay loam soil, and add 5.6 liters of 0.5% common salt solution to the soil. The ECE of the soil saturation extract should be 8-10 dS/m. Plant tolerant and susceptible checks.
- Add demineralized water whenever necessary.
- Score at 4 WT, using percentage of dead leaves and leaf injury symptoms (see table). □

Results of screening rice plants for tolerance for salinity, using a modified method. CNRRI, China, 1988.

Dead leaves ^a (%)	Reaction to salinity	Score	Tolerance degree
0-35	Normal growth, absence of salinity symptoms	1	Highly tolerant
36-50	Restricted growth and tillering, a few rolling leaves	3	Tolerant
51-70	Very restricted growth and tillering, most leaves rolling	5	Moderately tolerant
71-90	Growth ceases, most leaves and some plants dead	7	Moderately susceptible
91-100	Most plants dead or nearly dead	9	Susceptible

^aPercentage dead leaves = $\frac{\text{no. of dead leaves/plant}}{\text{no. of leaves/plant}} \times 100$.

Rice yield responses in a saline soil in Sri Lanka

A. H. G. Mithrasena and H. D. Jayawickrama, Regional Agricultural Research Centre, Bomбуwela, Sri Lanka

In the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka, 10% of riceland is coastal saline. Pokkali is one of the few adaptable varieties, particularly where soil conductivity goes up to 7-8 dS/m. However, Pokkali is not widely grown because it has low yields and is susceptible to lodging and diseases.

This study compared two promising salt-tolerant cultivars with Pokkali at 2 spacings in 1985-86 wet season in a farmer's field with salinity up to about 7 dS/m.

Two-week-old seedlings of Bw 272-8, Bw 297-2, and Pokkali from a dry bed